

EUROAGEISM H2020 project - ESR7 project Scientific Meeting and Training School

RATIONAL PRESCRIBING IN OLDER PATIENTS IN EUROPE AND OTHER COUNTRIES: core role of development of clinical pharmacy services in different settings of care for better individualisation of drug regimens in older patients

Tampere University, Tampere, Finland, February 2018

EUROAGEISM Horizon 2020 project entitled “An international, multi-disciplinary, multi-sectoral training network on ageism” focuses on aspects of ageism in European aging population. ESR7 project (7th scientific project) is devoted to “Inappropriate prescribing in older patients in different settings of care in Europe and on availability of medication safety and medication management services”. Assoc. Prof. Daniela Fialová from the Faculty of Pharmacy, Charles University in the Czech Republic and Early Stage Researcher (ESR7) Jovana Brkic manage these scientific works in collaboration with researchers from several EU and non-EU countries.

As one of the most effective ways how to reduce inappropriate prescribing in older patients is to systematically develop medication safety and medication management services for older adults in Europe in different settings of care, the ESR7 Training school in Tampere, Finland focused on **important role of clinical pharmacists in individualisation of drug regimens in complex older adults** and on strategies on how to develop clinical pharmacy services in Central and Eastern Europe. This training school was run on February 8-9th, 2019 and two scientific meetings followed on Feb 10-11th, 2019. Researchers and practitioners from Central and Eastern Europe took part in this event, namely from the Czech Republic, Estonia, Serbia, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia and Turkey. Experienced speakers were invited from Belgium, Finland, Czech Republic and Ireland. First two invited lectures were presented by Julie Hias from the University hospital Leuven, Belgium (speaker for the ESCP

instead of the President of the ESCP Bart van dem Bemt at this event) and Annemie Somers (Ghent University Hospital, Belgium) who provided information about **availability, practical aspects and development of clinical pharmacy services for older adults in acute care and ambulatory care practices**. Other two invited speakers from Finland, Marja Airaksinen and Maarit Dimitrow, devoted her lectures to **practical aspects of development of medication safety and medication management services in Finnish nursing homes and home care**. Maarit Dimitrow provided further training for participants on the use of the practical tool DRP-RAT used for initial identification of first medication-related problems by nurses that helps to identify patients in need of comprehensive medication reviews by clinical pharmacists.

The second day of ESR7 training school was devoted to principles of individualisation of drug regimens in complex older adults. Daniela Fialová from the Czech Republic presented lecture about changes in the efficiency and safety of drugs in older patients due to the ageing process of the organism and on individualisation of drug schemes. Jiří Vlček from the Czech Republic continued with his talk on implicit evaluation of drug regimens and risk management algorithms. In a conclusive lecture, Cristin Ryan from Ireland compared **applicability and content validity of different explicit tools of potentially inappropriate prescribing and their usefulness in daily clinical practice and research**. The ESR7 EUROAGEISM training school continued with two scientific meetings where ongoing research

works data management and data collection for years 2019-2020 were discussed. During this meeting, Jovana Brkic presented results from narrative literature review summarising studies on **inappropriate prescribing and potentially inappropriate medication use in older patients** in ESR7 EUROAGEISM countries. Then other country-specific research presentations followed, namely from Serbia, Turkey, Bulgaria, Estonia, Croatia, the Czech Republic and Slovak Republic. Clinical pharmacy services for older patients are low levels or not yet developed in some Central and Eastern European countries. More systematic approaches to ensure individualisation of drug regimens and availability of medication safety and medication management services is necessary. The ESR7 Training School of the EUROAGEISM H2020 project contributed to understanding of differences in various stages of development of clinical pharmacy services in different settings of care in Central and Eastern Europe, emphasized rational principles of drug prescribing in geriatric patients and stimulated lively discussions amongst participants and speakers on future ways how to improve appropriateness of drug prescribing for older adults in Europe. Participants got familiar with practical tools and methods helping to individualize drug regimens in geriatric patients.

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